

THE USE OF PROBLEMATIC EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ACTIVATION OF EDUCATIONAL AND COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF PUPILS IN THE LESSONS OF THEIR NATIVE LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY

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Abstract. this article gives information about utilizing problematic approach in teaching native language and reading literacy lessons as well as provides possible techniques how to conduct both lessons more productively.

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The integration of theoretical reasoning, practical application, and sensory experience is known as cognitive activity. It is implemented at every stage of life, in all forms of pupil interactions and activities (socially and productively beneficial labor, value-oriented and artistic-aesthetic activities, communication), as well as via carrying out different subject-practical tasks during the learning process [1].

Independence, which is linked to the definition of the goal, mode, and means of the activity by the pupils independently without assistance from adults or teachers, is another significant component of the motivation of pupils' learning that is closely related to activity. Cognitive engagement and self-reliance are intrinsically linked: children who participate in more school activities tend to be more self-reliant, whereas pupils who do not engage in enough activities become more reliant on others and lose their sense of autonomy.

Traditionally, activation is used to describe pupil activity management. The process of motivating pupils to study actively and purposefully, getting them over stereotyped and passive behaviors, and preventing mental work from declining or stagnating is known as activation. Activation's primary objective is to increase pupil participation, which enhances the standard of the educational process. [1]

Every step of a lesson should involve increasing the pupils' cognitive activity and piqueing their interest in learning through a variety of techniques, formats, and assignments especially when teachers teach them native and reading literacy. These

include a differentiated approach to teaching, individual pupil work, various didactic and illustrative materials, technical teaching tools, and more. It is essential that kids like learning in every class so they may grow to believe in their own abilities and be interested in learning new things.

One of the primary approaches to enhancing the educational process in schools is, therefore, to activate pupils' cognitive activity in the classroom. Pupils' active mental processes facilitate the conscious and long-lasting integration of their information. [2] The development of truly dialogical relations—that is, subject-subject, equal—in which the participants in the dialogue are interested in communicating with each other and see in the interlocutor an interesting person, a bearer of a different, valuable opinion, or another potentially valuable culture—is an essential component of a native language and reading literacy lessons. [3]

“A set of different options for interaction between the elements of the lesson that arises in the learning process and ensures its purposeful effectiveness” is the definition of the lesson's structure.

Within the framework of developmental learning theories, the educational scenario is acknowledged as a structural component of a contemporary lesson. In line with E.V. Karsalova, we define educational circumstances as every meaningful, well planned step in the arrangement of a school child's educational and reading activities, including cognitive tasks (i.e., establishing a goal and providing an approach to achieve it).

The first and most crucial component is the pupil's unique intellectual activity for the autonomous absorption of new concepts through problem-solving in the classroom. This provides awareness, depth, and strength of knowledge as well as the development of logical, theoretical, and intuitive thinking. The only true information that pupils acquire is that which they may deliberately apply to their future theoretical and practical endeavors.

The second benefit is that, since it fosters the development of critical, creative, and dialectical thinking skills, problem-based learning is the best method for shaping a worldview. Since only a dialectical approach to the investigation of all processes and phenomena of reality formulates a system of strong and profound beliefs, pupils' ability to solve problems on their own is also a prerequisite for the conversion of information into beliefs.

The third characteristic, which is based on the didactic idea of the integration of learning with life, emerges from the patterns of the interactions between theoretical and practical issues. Relationships with real-world experiences are crucial for generating challenging circumstances and act as benchmarks for assessing how well educational difficulties are solved.

The fourth characteristic of problem-based learning is the teacher's methodical use of the best possible mix of different pupil forms of independent work. This characteristic is that the instructor plans the completion of individual assignments that call for both updating already learned material and assimilating fresh concepts and methods of operation.

The individual approach's didactic premise dictates the fifth feature. The fundamental distinction between problem-based learning and traditional learning is that, in the former case, the teacher's frontal presentation of new information and the pupil's individual form of perception and assimilation of it create a dialectical contradiction that necessitates individualization.

Individualization in problem-based learning is primarily caused by the existence of learning problems with differing levels of complexity, which are interpreted differently by every learner. Different people will perceive the same problem differently, which will influence how it is formulated, what kinds of hypotheses are put out, and how further evidence is found.

The dynamism of problem-based learning, or the movable interconnectedness of its components, is its sixth characteristic. Because of the dialectical rule of the interconnectedness and interdependence of all objects and phenomena of the material world, one scenario automatically gives way to another, which is the dynamic of problem-based learning.

Traditional learning lacks dynamism and, as some studies have noted, instead of being troublesome, “categoricity” is dominant.

The pupil's high emotional activity is the seventh characteristic. This is because the problem situation itself is what arouses the pupil's emotions, and it is also because the pupil's active mental activity is inherently linked to the sensory-emotional domain of mental activity. A pupil's personal experience and emotional activity are triggered by any autonomous, inquiring mental activity that is linked to a personal “acceptance” of an educational challenge. Consequently, brain activity is determined by emotional activity.

The second path of cognition is strengthened by the new ratio of induction and deduction that problem-based learning offers, along with the new ratio of reproductive and productive—which includes creative assimilation of knowledge—which increases the role of pupils' creative cognitive activity. This is the eighth feature of problem-based learning. [4].

In conclusion, the first benefit of problem-based learning is that it fosters a strong knowledge base and unique way of thinking. The second benefit is that it fosters deep beliefs. The third benefit is that it fosters the creative application of information in real-world situations. These three characteristics guarantee that the school's primary mission is accomplished and have the highest societal value. The first three acts' efficiency is determined by the major five qualities, which are of a socio-didactic nature.

Three basic types of problem-based learning are recognized in pedagogy: partial search activity in laboratory work or during an experiment; problematic presentation of instructional content in a lecture or seminar; and autonomous research activity. A problem seminar might take the shape of a theoretical game, in which pupils arrange small working groups to demonstrate to one another the benefits of their concept and approach. A practical lesson devoted to the verification or evaluation of a particular theoretical model or technique, the degree of their usefulness in these settings, can be applied to the solving of a set of challenging problems. [4].

The complexity of fixing an issue in a problematic scenario might vary. Such a learning environment entails the maximum level of problemativeness, where a learner formulates the problem (task) and discovers its solution on their own, as well as determines and assesses their own decision-making.

Problematic scenarios stem from pupils' active cognitive engagement, which entails identifying and resolving intricate problems that call for analysis, up-to-date information, the capacity to recognize connections in seemingly disparate data, etc.

The following scenarios might occur as a difficulty in the lesson:

- difficult tasks with redundant, contradictory, missing, or purposefully manufactured faults;
 - the quest for the truth (method, method, rules of solution);
 - divergent viewpoints on the same subject;
 - inconsistencies in the practical activity.
- [5].

A teacher can expose pupils to challenging situations in the following ways:

- an energizing conversation serves as a “excavator” that unearths an issue, query, or challenge, assisting in the creation of an instructional job;
- the use of motivating techniques: “bright spot”
- the message of intriguing material (historical facts, legends, etc.); demonstration of incomprehensible phenomena (experiment, visibility); “actualization”;
- the discovery of the meaning and significance of the problem for pupils;
- a leading dialogue: a logically constructed chain of tasks and questions is a “locomotive” moving towards new knowledge, a way of action.

The following are the primary prerequisites for using challenging situations:

Pupils' involvement in: a novel subject (“discovery” of fresh information);

- the capacity of pupils to recognize the region of “ignorance” in a new assignment;
- the ability to apply previously learned knowledge to a new setting;
- active search activity.

The teacher's responsibilities include:

- creating and managing problematic situations during the lesson;
- formulating the problem situation by pointing out to pupils the reasons why the assigned practical educational task was not completed or why they were unable to explain certain demonstrated facts to them.

The way in which training sessions are organized, with pupils actively and independently solving challenging situations while being guided by an instructor, leads to a creative mastery of professional knowledge, skills, and abilities as well as the growth of thinking abilities. A difficult situation consists of the subject and object of cognition and their mental interactions.

In addition to promoting cognitive issues that pupils actively solve to integrate new knowledge, problem-based learning also aims to support pupils' autonomous quest for new information and behavioral patterns. So far, the most promising approach is problem-based learning.

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